

Enhancing Project Completion Success and Career Development in Commercial Banks of Swat Valley Pakistan through Emotional Intelligence Training

Muhammad Nawaz

Department of Management Science and Engineering, Shandong Normal University,
Shandong, Jinan, China

Liu Fing Ming

Faculty of Business School, Department of Management Science and Engineering, Shandong
Normal University, China

Adnan Alfaisal

Department of Management Science and Engineering, Shandong Normal University,
Shandong, Jinan, China

Sher Khan

Faculty of Management, Comenius University, Bratislava, Slovakia

Mohammad Hanif Khan

Faculty of Hotel and Tourism Management Department, University of Malakand, Chakdara

Saud Alfaisal

Department of Management Science, COMSATS Institute of Information Technology Virtual
Campus Islamabad-Pakistan

Samreen Hayat

Department of Social and Gender studies,
University of Swat

ABSTRACT: This research study aims to investigate the potential link between emotional intelligence training and project completion success as well as career development in the context of commercial banks operating in Swat Valley, Pakistan. Emotional intelligence has been recognized as a vital skill for professional growth and interpersonal effectiveness, making it relevant for employees in the banking sector. This research utilized a mixed-methods approach, incorporating both quantitative data collection through surveys to measure changes in emotional intelligence levels after training and qualitative interviews to explore the perceived impact of emotional intelligence on project outcomes and career progression. 200 respondents were employed during the study by stratified sampling technique. To assess emotional intelligence of employees, test was designed by reviewing Daniel Goleman's emotional intelligence model which is based upon four main constructs including: self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and relationship management. The findings of this study offers valuable insights into the role of emotional intelligence training in fostering successful project completion and facilitating career development within the commercial banking sector of Swat Valley.

Key words: Emotional Intelligence, Successful Project, Subjective Success, Objective Success.

Introduction

Literature review

Research Methodology

Data Analysis And Research Findings

Findings And Discussion

Conclusion & Recommendations

References

1. Introduction

We never stop experiencing, working, learning, and growing during our entire existence. These advancements eventually result in development, when adjustments are polished and transformed. The idea of development becomes more complicated when it is applied to the working world since it demands an individual to continually evaluate, study, manage, improve, and grow in their specific field. Career development is often referred to as professional growth. It's a continuous process throughout life where one keeps developing and evolving. In the past, career growth was thought to involve joining a company, moving up the corporate ladder, and advancing through well-defined job titles and hierarchies. However, as time went on, the term's scope grew more expansive. According to Wendy Patton and Mary McMohan (2006) Career development was described by the Department of Education and Science in 1989 as "multiple occupational roles which an individual play throughout the life; like student, part-time worker, employee, and independent professional, etc.," Although Donald Super's definition of career development as "occupational and non-occupational progress of an individual through variety of roles; a student move with different levels, acquire education, learn, select a profession, and grow in respective field" was also quoted in the same book. Additionally, Super had emphasized social duties as a crucial rung on the job development ladder (Patton & McMohan, 2006). The new field of career development where it is linked to general learning and growth is this one. However, if we limit our focus for this research to career success, which is a subset of career growth, even then, it is no longer as simple as it once was for an individual to advance in a certain sector. The idea has altered because to shifting business requirements; organizational perspective has moved from specialization to generalization, for which people must continue to learn more in order to advance to higher organizational levels. People in this race for success prefer to move with possibilities for growth, development, and success rather than remaining in the same position or industry for an extended period of time. The pressures placed on organizations have altered due to the competitive climate. Individuals are now expected to have emotional intelligence in order to comprehend organizational dynamics and appreciate the culture and people, in addition to having the mental and physical capacity to learn and use technical skills. People nowadays must be able to operate under pressure and maintain control over both themselves and other people since work life is stressful. This idea of emotional intelligence was taken from Goleman's work, which maintains that emotional intelligence is a predictor of job success, by Jordan, Ashton-James, and Ashkanasy (n.d.). It has been stated that while cognitive intelligence can aid in employment, emotional intelligence plays a key impact in promotion. Although the relationship between high IQ and excellent job performance has been questioned in the past, professional success is now taken into account because an employee's primary objective is to perform and advance in their particular sector. Despite having exceptional performance, job success is often hidden since greater IQ and performance are not the only factors at play. EI also plays a significant part in it. Researchers have shown that cognitive intelligence, as opposed to emotional intelligence (EI), is a stronger predictor of professional and academic achievement. However, Stys & Brown (2004) assert that emotional intelligence is a more potent predictor of success than cognitive intelligence when it comes to performance excellence or being an excellent leader. Even after so many studies and the word "EI" being accepted in the profession,

there are still many of disagreements over what the notion actually means. Particularly when it comes to the link between EI and job success, even empirical data is insufficient to demonstrate this association. Goleman defined emotional intelligence (EI) in terms of four components, which are: personal emotional awareness, responsiveness to the feelings of others, management of one's own and others' emotions, and social skills, which are necessary to manage one's own emotions and those of others (Gosling, 2006). Zeidner, Matthews, and Robert (2004) make the case that elements of emotional intelligence have a significant role in both one's ability to perform well at work and in the development of one's own leadership abilities. The most crucial components in the equation for job success are leadership and performance. Success of people helps a country flourish, but institutional framework is also crucial for this development. Industries have a significant impact on a country's success. The development of Pakistan's economy depends on a number of industries, including textile, sports products, services, and agriculture. The banking sector contributes significantly to the service sector. Even though the banking industry is expanding quickly, this tension is being felt throughout the business. Employees that are under a lot of job pressure have poorer productivity and act out more, which is detrimental to the success of the firm. As Goleman (1998) indicated, "emotional intelligence as propensity to control personal emotions and of others as well" will be tested in this study in relation to how emotional intelligence offers defense against such scenarios.

Statement of Problem

In the commercial banking sector of Swat Valley, there exists a significant challenge related to project completion success and career development. Despite the industry's competitive nature and the importance of project outcomes, several issues hinder progress. Employees often struggle with handling workplace stress, building effective relationships, and adapting to evolving job requirements. Additionally, leadership within banks may lack the emotional intelligence skills necessary to guide teams successfully. This lack of emotional intelligence, both at the employee and leadership levels, poses a barrier to achieving optimal project outcomes and career growth. The need for a structured approach to enhance emotional intelligence through training becomes evident to address these challenges and create a more resilient, adaptable, and successful workforce within Swat Valley's commercial banks.

Therefore, this study aims to explore the impact of emotional intelligence training on project completion success and career development within commercial banks in Swat Valley, proposing a solution to improve overall performance, reduce employee turnover, and foster effective leadership within the banking sector.

Objectives of study

The purpose of the study is to find out:

- Enhance the successful completion of projects within commercial banks by implementing emotional intelligence training programs among employees.
- Type of correlation between emotional intelligence and effective project management.

- Role of emotional intelligence in managing projects effectively.
- Impact of emotional intelligence on improving the quality of project.

Significance of the Study

The commercial banking sector plays a vital role in the economic development of Swat Valley. Improving project completion success and career development within these banks can lead to more efficient use of financial resources and increased profitability, contributing to the overall economic growth of the region. Emotional intelligence training equips employees with better stress management, decision-making, and interpersonal skills. This can lead to improved project outcomes, reduced project failures, and increased client satisfaction, which are critical for the long-term success of commercial banks. This study contributes valuable insights to the field of organizational psychology and human resource management by examining the impact of emotional intelligence training on project success and career development in a specific regional context. In conclusion, a study on enhancing project completion success and career development through emotional intelligence training in commercial banks of Swat Valley holds great significance for the local economy, workforce stability, and the overall well-being of the community. It has the potential to drive positive change in the banking sector and serve as a model for similar initiatives in other industries and regions.

Definitions of key terms

Emotional Intelligence (EI): competence to identify, judge, handle personal and other's emotions.

Emotional Quotient (EQ): measure of non-cognitive abilities (Emotional Intelligence).

Intelligence Quotient (IQ): measure of cognitive abilities (intelligence).

The Mayer-Salovey-Caruso Emotional Intelligence Test (MSCEIT): determines emotional intelligence keeping ability as parameter. This test is designed to measure Emotional Intelligence based on model of EI given by Mayer and Salovey.

2. Literature Review

Introduction to Intelligence

"The ability to recognize one's own and other people's feelings and use this capability to motivate, direct oneself, and influence others in associations" (Goleman, 1998). According to Salovey and Mayer (1990). Emotional intelligence is "the division of communal intelligence that involves the skill to observe personal feelings, to differentiate among them, and to use this information," The term "intelligence," according to Gardner, is employed differently by various individuals, but it always refers to acquiring knowledge and comprehending it through mental capacity. The concept was defined by many scholars from the same point of view, but with more technical language. Wechsler described intelligence as the "collective aptitude of an individual to act persistently, to think logically and to respond to environment accordingly". Scientific definition of intelligence is; "intellectual skill

that allow the identification, wisdom, recollection of knowledge and the ability to rationale for specific appearance of knowledge". (Mayer, Richards & Barsade, 2008)

Emotional Intelligence

The cognitive aspect of intelligence has continued to draw the interest of psychologists and scholars. Because memory and problem solving were the only models available for determining an individual's effectiveness in the past, psychologists have concentrated on these aspects of intelligence. But as time went on, academics' attention shifted to emotional intelligence. It speaks to the sensible use of both our own and other people's feelings. The definition of emotion is "feeling arising as result of experience from external environment and self-awareness." (Mayer, Roberts & Barsade, 2008). The opposite of cognitive capacity is intelligence. Motivation, emotion, and cognition are the three categories into which the human brain's functions are divided. Motivations result from both internal and external bodily states (basic needs), emotions constantly change signals and react to changes in the environment and the individual, but cognition, the third category of mental operation, is about learning from the environment and solving problems. The definition of emotion is frequently expanded by integrating it with characteristics of motivation and cognition. Mayer, Carsuo and Salovey (1999) proposed "feelings are resultant of a person's internal, external environment, understanding and understanding capability". Emotions are essential to organizational work environment as emotions involve some attributes of motivation, emotion influence action, and above all emotion also play role in career development (Brown, George & Smith, 2003). In "working with emotional intelligence", Goleman (1998) highlighted importance of feelings in decision making.

Career Development and Career Success

It has been demonstrated by a number of research that emotional intelligence has affected project success. Goleman (1995) is of the opinion, strongly holds, that it (emotional intelligence) has been the cause of man's success. The team members of the project manager will have a positive approach; in case their managers have good emotional intelligence. According to Sy et al., (2006) manager's emotional intelligence brings about a more positive effect on representatives. It has been taken by Berman and West (2008) as a social capability and it has concentrated an impact in administration. It has been noted as a crucial characteristic for work in a certain role. According to Dong, Shao, Yuan, and Huang (2014), the heightened emotional intelligence level of team members may make it less acceptable for them to turn over goals that were crucial to the project's success. Wong and Law (2002) found the extremely necessary link between emotional intelligence and job fulfilment and work performance. According to Patra (2004) it (emotional intelligence) can create a very healthy and effective working environment and can bring about satisfaction in the team members and can create good administration or well organized expansion. Sy et al., (2006) analysed the link among worker's emotional intelligence, the emotional intelligence of their leader, and work performance. The result was that the team member's emotional intelligence was inextricably connected with work satisfaction and success.

According to Quick and Nelson (2009), a person's ability to influence the performance, fulfilment, and growth of the project team increases with their level of team

cohesiveness. As they told attentively to the generation criteria, such personnel would have a propensity of more steady or regular yield amongst its peers. Sharing knowledge also modulates the relationship between individual performance and team cohesiveness. The ability of the team to predict project performance, team effectiveness, and work satisfaction in a project context is not entirely evident, though. Whereby, time and project supply are the limitation (Woerkom & Sanders, 2009). Keeping in view that outcome control urges the uniqueness of accomplishing project objectives; the employees having no practice and insufficiency, will as a matter of fact do not understand these objectives in lack of the individual who know about the improvement (Wallace, Keil & Rei, 2004). People in cohesive teams are drawn to hard labor by force. Performance and maintenance are closely related to team cohesiveness (Beal, Cohen, Burke, & McLendon, 2003). Team cohesiveness was employed by Carron, Colman, and Loughhead (2001) as a mediator between emotional intelligence and project performance. In a similar vein, team cohesiveness was employed by Dolan, Tzafir, and Mach (2010) as a mediator between employee attitude and project success. On the other hand, it has been discovered that a more cohesive team produces better outcomes, which in turn leads to project success.

Career Development and Career Success

The term career has its roots in educational reforms (Nevitt, 1967). According to research on personal growth, education is a component of evolution. The author went on to explain it as a plan for progress rather than just a way to teach people skills and information. As people's worry for their achievement grew, so did their interest in education. However, education is not guarantee of success (Bradshaw, 2011). To be successful there must be a match between knowledge and knowledge of professional world (Parson, 1909). Idea was proposed by Frank Parson; well known for his book "Choosing a Vocation." Author identified three elements; self-knowledge, knowledge of relevant field and "what is the relation between two facts" (Parson, 1909). Parson regarded these three elements as essential in career selection. He further emphasized it is better to choose a vocation than merely to hunt a job. Throughout 1900 to 1950 most of the work was done over individual's trait and environmental factor. Gradually researches started to contemplate over characteristics of the individuals who select the career rather than what is to be chosen. (Edwin, 2001).

Ginzberget. al proposed career selection as a process that take place in three stages; fantasy stage, tentative stage and realistic stage (overview of career development theory, n.d).Sarah Senghas, in her article (Using the Ginzberg theory of Occupational Choice to determine your Career Path, 2007) proposed; at fantasy stage an individual possess strong imagination power however individual is incapable to understand practicality of life. This phase involves identification and evaluation of different options. Afterwards next phase is tentative, which involves selection of career field. The last level, which is the realistic one, is when an individual pursues training and study in a particular sector of interest. The three more stages of investigation, crystallization, and specification make up the realistic stage.

Donald Super was a significant contribution to career theories as well. Growth (childhood), exploration (youth), establishing (early adulthood), maintenance (middle

adulthood), and decline stage (older adulthood) were the five developmental phases first described in Super (1954). Additionally, Super had recommended appropriate tasks for each step. The total of all the roles we perform in our life is how Super views a career. Super introduced the idea of professional maturity. (Patton & Lokan, 2001). He emphasized career maturity as life long process. Super's work was over development, self-concept and contextual perspective. Super proposed an individual's personal view regarding self-varies, improves and keeps building up throughout the individual's life as a result of experience, and one adapts changes in career accordingly.

Subjective and Objective Career Success

Career achievement is subset of career (Urs & Laurie, 1989); defined career as the desirable result at some point in individual's work experiences over time, this holds two perspectives which Oxford English Dictionary (2011) defined as "an occupation undertaken for a significant period of a person's life and with opportunities for progress," and "the attainment of fame, wealth, or social status." This definition has two perspectives one refers self-satisfaction and other refers to success as opulence that largely relies on societal status. Everett Hughes (1937, 1958) under theoretical framework has categorized career success as subjective and objective success. Hughes represented objective career as the one which is easily visible, quantifiable and demonstrable in term of promotions, compensation and position; such success serves as milestone of career across societies (Helsin, 2005). However subjective career success deals with personal factors such as satisfaction in professional life, flexibility, learning, and these personal factors have acquired more significance nowadays (Hall & Chandler, 2005). However, every individual is different from other and since the career aspirations as well. Some weigh job security and compensation over work-life balance. Similarly, there are the individuals with contradictory perspective. Traditionally researches were having in their mind career success is one where an individual acquires higher hierarchical position, promotion, rank, job retention and compensation (Hall & Chandler, 2005). However, wind of technological advancement and globalization revolutionized human needs which lead to change in organizational priorities with respect to employee compliance. Organizations have identified need of attention toward subjective success (Hall, 1996).

Subjective career success is resultant of individual to work experiences (Hughes, 1937, 1958). It reflects individual's perception regarding direction of career that where career is moving and where it shall lead (Stebbins, 1970). Thorndike (1934) emphasized over importance of subjective and objective career success that is measurable in terms of job satisfaction, earnings and job status as objective career success criterion (Helsin, 2005). Hughes also concentrated over providing basis for understanding and mentioning the importance of objective career and subjective career. Both the views subjective and objective; are precise, none of them is superior over other and neither is good or bad (Hall & Chandler 2005). Career success is not only described with two distinct views but researchers have focused on interdependence of the two as well. Barley (1989), proposed looking at the one aspect of career goes against the Hughes's original concepts (Arthur, Khapova & Wilderom, 2005.) Individuals continuously interpret their career success and work experiences. They get familiar with career goals, develop their own success definition and proceed accordingly. Lawrence (1984, 1996) introduced "age norms". It refers to

continuous process that starts with entrance of an employee in organization where an individual interact, socialize, develop understanding of organizational norms and start to progress toward subjective career success that eventually lead to objective career experiences. (Arthur, Khapova & Wilderom, 2005). Changing job needs are the stimulator of various theoretical developments, concepts of boundary less career (Arthur, Khapova, & Wilderom, 2005) protean career (Hall, 2004) and social capital theory (Seibert, Kraimer & Liden, 2001) are resultant of it.

Theoretical Framework

Referred to above mentioned measures of emotional intelligence, MSCEIT is the test to assess contribution of emotional intelligence in one's ability. Here ability refers to capability of understanding, learning, improving and developing. From the very inception we start to adapt from our surrounding, we learn and we develop. This development goes along with us until we die. Development is a lifelong process in every sphere whether it's personal or professional. One of the most important factors that lead to development is motivation. This motivation could be in term of physical object or subjective satisfaction. All individual has own need which lie at different level of Maslow's hierarchy; ranging from physiological needs to safety and security, social activity, to esteem, and finally to self-actualization. Through these needs individual formulate own success definition. Achievement of needs serves as sense of accomplishment and success. Similar to success, career success also has two aspects; objective and subjective. In current protean era subjective success has acquired more value. As referred earlier work environment is changing and organizational requirements are also changing. Organizations want individuals to not only to work over conventional procedure in isolation but they want individuals to be capable of moving with changing everyday requirements and comply with people. When it comes to work with people in organizational settings and progress along; in addition to personal characteristic and cognitive intelligence, individuals need to be emotionally intelligent as well.

Protean Career Theory

The protean career theory proposed psychological career success is outcome of efforts of individuals for career management (Hall, 1996, 2004). Protean career contradicts to concept of career development which emphasize individual development is responsibility of organizations only. A model was proposed by Brisco and Hall having individual's attitude towards career management which involves both others directed and a self-motivated attitude (Brisco, Hall & Demuth, 2006). Protean career theory focuses on individual's self-management of career in self-motivated manner with respect to values and evaluation of success depending upon subjective criterion of career success (Briscoe & Hall, 2006; Hall, 2004). Individuals having conventional approach toward career, lean to have submissive role in career progression. However individual with proactive attitude take responsibility of career choice and opportunities (Hall, 2004). Individual need to be aware of self, as it is the best guideline in career verdict (Hall, 2004). Development of flexible approach is essential for right career selection. Protean attitude provides base for initiatives taken by individuals as par career management, might include development of learning about oneself and about taking actions for managing career.

Social Capital Theory

Social capital theory has three approaches weak tie, structural whole and social resource theory. (Seibert & Kramair, 2001) Ties in which information moves outside the network are referred to be weak ties that reach outside of one's social elite (Granovetter, 2004). However, Granovetter (1973) proposed weak knots develop wider network. Structural whole theory highlighted weak ties provide greater information, negotiation advantage and thus lead to more control over the situation. In weak knots there is little concern toward the work among groups however flow of information is strong. (Burt, 1992) Whereas social resource theory introduced new dimension where not only the tie but the human resource involve in knot effects the outcome, it depends on individual to how to utilize available social capital for career success. For career success extroversion, pro-activity and cognitive intelligence has relation to both the approaches of career success. (Sorrrenson, 2005)

3. Research Methodology

This study used a quantitative research design to investigate the impact of emotional intelligence on successfully completing projects and to present empirical data demonstrating the relationships between the variables. Through closed-ended questions, respondents' emotional intelligence and degree of professional success were determined; the gathered answers were then evaluated using a Likert scale. Relevant statistical procedures, such as average, percentage, regression analysis, and correlation analysis, were employed to investigate the link between the variables. Additionally, a confidence test was conducted at 5% intervals in order to determine the relationship.

For this specific study, developmental areas of Swat have been chosen for field surveys and interviews. Swat is a river valley and administrative district of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, province of Pakistan. The valley of Swat is located in the north of K.P.K, 35° North Latitude and 72° and 30° East Longitude, and is surrounded by the sky-high mountains. Chitral and Gilgit are located in the north, Dir in the west, and Mardan in the south, while Indus separates it from Hazara in the East. The region possessed a multicultural historic environment, with evidence of settlement since long before it became in succession part of the Pakistan. This research was limited to only Tehsil Babuzai of District Swat.

The research was conducted over employees of Bank Alfalah Limited, Allied Bank Limited, United Bank Limited, Muslim Commercial Bank Limited, Habib Bank Limited, The Bank of Khyber and Habib Metropolitan Bank Limited. Since the banking industry is one of the most profitable, it was chosen for study. The research population comprised management cadre workers of commercial banks. Only workers who have been employed by the bank for two or more years were included in the sampling period. Both male and female participants were included in the diverse sample used in this study. In this study, non-probability sampling with convenient sampling method was employed.

Sample size

Participants in the study were two hundred bank workers who were members of the management cadre of the chosen commercial banks in Pakistan's Swat Valley. Two hundred was the chosen sample size after previous research articles were reviewed. The sampling frame comprised middle-level managers from various commercial banks in the Swat Valley. Scope of sample for this research was confined to seven banks including, Bank Alfalah Limited, Allied Bank Limited, United Bank Limited, Muslim Commercial Bank Limited, Habib Bank Limited, The Bank of Khyber and Habib Metropolitan Bank Limited. Daniel Goleman's paradigm, which he introduced in his book Emotional Intelligence, was used to help construct the emotional intelligence exam. After the data was analyzed, a comprehensive report was produced that showed how respondents' career success and project completion were impacted by their emotional intelligence.

4. Data Analysis And Research Findings

DATA ANALYSIS

Analysis of more than two hundred responses was done in accordance with the study strategy. On the other hand, only 19.55% of the 200 questionnaires distributed were returned, and an analysis of 19.55% of the replies was done. Since several of the comments did not fit within the management cadre, they were removed. Bank staff members were given questionnaires, irrespective of their gender. Data study shows that in a few commercial banks in Pakistan's Swat Valley, there are more men than women in the management cadre. Only 8% of the 200 responders in the survey were female, with 92% of them being men in various administrative positions, from cashier to assistant vice president (AVP).

Figure 4-1: Respondents Proportion on Gender Basis

A review of the respondents' ages reveals that the majority of them fell between the ages of 25 and 35, which suggests that respondents typically exhibit more adaptable

behavior. The age distribution of the respondents was as follows: 68% were between the ages of 25 and 35, 14% were under 25, 9% were between the ages of 35 and 45, and the remaining respondents were above 45. It may be shown graphically as follows:

Figure 4-2: Respondents proportion age wise

When it comes to experience, the majority of respondents have between two and five years under their belt. Merely 9% of the participants have more than eleven years of expertise.

Figure 4-3: Respondents Proportion Experience wise

The study's main goal was to investigate respondents' emotional intelligence, and to that end, questions were created using Daniel Goleman's methodology. Emotional intelligence comprises several dimensions such as self-awareness, self-management, social skills, and internet usage. The majority of responders have above-average levels of emotional stability, according to the data gathered. There was not a single responder with a

low emotional intelligence rating, despite the extremely small number of respondents falling between the extremes of high and medium emotional intelligence.

Figure 4-4: Emotional Intelligence level of Respondents

When emotional intelligence is further examined in relation to age groups, it is revealed that respondents under the age of two have lower emotional intelligence than the other age groups. According to their age, the respondents' average emotional intelligence is as follows:

Figure 4-5: Emotional Intelligence level of Respondents with varying Age Brackets

According to this study, experience level has no impact on emotional intelligence. The emotional intelligence levels of respondents with two to eleven years of experience were nearly identical. Even though those with eight to eleven years of experience were less

emotionally intelligent than the others, the number of people in this experience category was too small to draw any meaningful conclusions.

Figure 4-6: Emotional Intelligence level of Respondents with varying Experience Level

Moreover, analysis of emotional intelligence with reference to hygiene and motivation factors reveals individuals, who prefer hygiene factors are more emotionally intelligent than those who prefer motivational factors.

Figure 4-7: Emotional Intelligence Level of Respondents with reference to Hygiene and Motivation Factor

Analysis of average emotional intelligence level of female versus male shows women were more emotionally intelligent rather than male respondents.

Figure 4-8: Emotional Intelligence Level of Respondent-gender wise

Career success was another research variable. The majority of respondents were content with their job accomplishments, according to an analysis of career success. Nonetheless, a very small proportion of participants was classified as unsuccessful, or more accurately, dissatisfied, since subjective success—which is linked to motivational factors—was prioritized above actual success in this instance. Salary and benefits, working conditions, work-life balance, the caliber of supervision, job responsibility, and recognition were all considered success parameters in this study.

Figure 4-9: Career Success level of Respondents

Analysis of career success to the age shows positive relation among two. Individual falling in age bracket of 35-45 years and over the age of 45 years possess more success.

Figure 4-10: Career Success level of Respondents with varying Age Bracket

The above result could be attributable to decreasing motivational level with increasing age. Analysis of career success with reference to experience also shows positive relation. Graphically, it can be presented as follow:

Figure 4-11: Career Success level of Respondents with varying Experience

Moreover, analysis of average career success to gender shows, female respondents were more successful than male respondents. They were satisfied with their achievements and they also had higher level of emotional intelligence.

Figure 4-12: Career Success level of Respondents Gender wise

Hygiene and motivational elements were used to conduct a more thorough examination of professional achievement. After the data was averaged, it was shown that people who favored motivating variables had somewhat higher success rates than those who chose hygienic factors.

Figure 4-13 Career Success level of Respondents with respect to Hygiene and Motivational Factors

5. Findings And Discussion

Regression Line

Up until now, it has been a separate summary of respondents' emotional intelligence and job performance. The study's main conclusions, however, are dependent on how emotional intelligence and professional performance are related. There is a

correlation between job success and emotional intelligence, according to regression analysis of the variables.

Figure 4-14: Regression Graph showing Relationship between Career Success and Emotional Intelligence Level

Correlation Analysis

A correlation study was performed to investigate the nature of the link between the two variables, and the results showed a relationship of 0.18. It suggests a favorable relationship between the variables. However, the relationship between emotional intelligence and job success is not as strong as it may be. The table below demonstrates the significant correlation between social skills and networking and career success.

Table 4-1 Co-relation Matrix show relationship between EI, Components of EI and CS

<i>Correlation Matrix</i>						
<i>Variables</i>	EI	CS	SA	SM	SS	N
Emotional Intelligence(EI)	1					
Career Success (CS)	0.18	1				
Self-awareness (SA)	0.60	-0.01	1			
Self-management (SM)	0.65	0.03	0.30	1		
Social Skills (SS)	0.57	0.17	0.30	0.21	1	
Networking (N)	0.70	0.23	0.18	0.21	0.22	1

Table 4-2 Co-relation Matrix showing relationship between CS, Components of CS and EI

<i>Correlation Matrix</i>										
<i>Variables</i>	EI	CS	SD	WLB	VP	R	J	LW	PB	G
Emotional Intelligence(EI)	1									
Career Success(CS)	0.18	1								
Self-development at work(SD)	0.05	0.38	1							
Work-life balance(WLB)	0.09	0.43	0.33	1						

Vertical Progression(VP)	0.02	0.49	0.34	0.40	1				
Recognition(R)	0.03	0.42	0.25	0.35	0.65	1			
Job itself(J)	0.01	0.36	0.44	0.19	0.44	0.40	1		
Learning at workplace(LW)	0.03	0.33	0.31	0.16	0.25	0.28	0.39	1	
Pay & Benefits(PB)	0.08	0.40	0.28	0.18	0.58	0.41	0.39	0.24	1

Above table shows relationship between career success components and Emotional intelligence, although relationship is not strong, but yet there is positive relation. A general overview of relationship between career success and emotional intelligence level of respondents was presented, however results of male and female respondents separately were as follow:

Table 4-3 Co-relation Matrix showing relationship between EI and CS of Male Respondents

Correlation Between Career Success and Emotional Intelligence of Male Respondents	Average
Emotional Intelligence	68
Career Success	75
Correlation	0.11
Self-Awareness	-0.10
Self-Management	0.01
Social Skills	0.17
Networking	0.16

Analysis male respondent's career success to emotional intelligence indicates a positive relation of 0.11. Also the relation between career success and networking and career success and social skills is much positive as compare to self-management.

Table 4-4 Co-relation Matrix showing relationship between EI and CS of Female Respondents

Correlation Between Career Success and Emotional Intelligence of Female Respondents	Average
Emotional Intelligence	70
Career Success	76
Correlation	0.43
Self-Awareness	0.28
Self-Management	0.09
Social Skills	0.15
Networking	0.48

Strong correlation of Emotional intelligence level to the career success level was observed in female respondents. Overall observation shows a positive relationship between career success and emotional intelligence, which further proven from the results of female respondents.

Coefficient of Determination

The result of applying the coefficient of determination was $r^2 = .03 = 3\%$. According to this figure, it is possible to identify the 3% difference in job success that results from differences in emotional intelligence levels, and vice versa. The results were further evaluated at a 5% confidence level to ensure their validity.

Hypothesis Testing

For this research following hypothesis was constructed.

H0: There is no relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Career Success.

H1: There is relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Career Success.

To test the hypothesis F-test was used.

Table 4-5 Table for F-test

	Sum of Squares(SS)	d.f	Mean Square	F=statistic	F-test(at .05)	p-value
Explained Regression	12.61	1	12.61	11.66	254	0.23
unexplained (error)	22043.32	150	146.96			
Total	22055.93					

According to the results, the null hypothesis might not be rejected since the p-value was larger than the significance level of .05. Additionally, the value of the f-test was greater than the f-value. It suggests that there is no connection between respondents' levels of job success and emotional intelligence. The hypothesis may be rejected at the 95% confidence level; nonetheless, correlation analysis reveals a weak but favorable association between professional success and emotional intelligence.

6. Conclusion & Recommendations

A positive correlation between job success and emotional intelligence is seen based on the established model. The study's key conclusion was the significant correlation between female respondents' professional performance and emotional intelligence. Additionally, an F-test was used to create and assess the connection hypothesis's validity at a 95% confidence range. H0: There isn't a relationship between career success and emotional intelligence. H1: There is a relationship between career success and emotional intelligence. The hypothesis test revealed that there is no association between the variables based on the specified model. link study, however, found a favorable relationship between job success and emotional intelligence; in fact, a single emotional intelligence component had a very strong link with the degree of career success. The main finding of the research

indicates that emotional intelligence is not the only element that determines professional success; other aspects also play a significant role. In this study, subjective success was given more weight than objective success. This study has opened up new avenues for investigation into the link between emotional intelligence and age, gender, and emotional intelligence level, as well as the function that emotional intelligence plays in objective success and employee performance. Furthermore, the results of this study may also be verified using several emotional intelligence models. To enhance project completion success and foster career development in the commercial banks of Swat Valley, it is crucial to implement emotional intelligence training as a core strategy. Firstly, commercial banks should invest in comprehensive emotional intelligence training programs for their employees. These programs should not only focus on understanding and managing one's emotions but also emphasize empathy, effective communication, and interpersonal skills. By equipping bank professionals with a higher level of emotional intelligence, they can better navigate complex client relationships, manage their teams more effectively, and make sound decisions, all of which are critical components for project success. Furthermore, banks in Swat Valley should encourage a culture of continuous learning and development. To support career growth, employees should have access to ongoing emotional intelligence training and resources. In addition, performance evaluations and promotion criteria should incorporate emotional intelligence competencies as key factors. This approach will incentivize employees to enhance their emotional intelligence skills, as it is directly linked to career advancement. Additionally, creating mentorship programs within the banks can help junior employees learn from experienced colleagues who have successfully integrated emotional intelligence into their careers, further promoting career development and project completion success. By investing in emotional intelligence training and integrating it into the culture of the commercial banks, Swat Valley can empower its banking professionals to excel in their careers while ensuring project success through enhanced interpersonal skills and decision-making abilities.

7. References

1. Arthur, M. B., & Rousseau, D. M. (1996). *The boundary less career: A new employment principle for a new organizational era*. Oxford University Press. New York.
2. Arthur, M. B., Khapova, S. N., & Wilderom, C. P. M. (2005). Career success in a boundary less career world [pdf]. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*.
3. Barley, S. R. (1989). Careers identities, and institutions: the legacy of the Chicago School of Sociology. In Arthur, M.B., Hall, D.T., & Lawrence, B.S. ed. *Handbook of career theory*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
4. Bar-On, R. (2006). The Bar-On model of emotional-social intelligence (ESI). *Consortium for Research on Emotional Intelligence in Organizations*, vol.18.
5. Bradshaw, J. (2011). University education no guarantee of earnings success.
6. Briscoe, J. P., & Hall, D. T. (2006). The interplay of boundary less and protean careers: Combinations and implications [pdf]. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*.
7. Briscoe, J. P., Hall, D. T., & DeMuth, R. L. F. (2006). Protean and boundary less careers: An empirical exploration [pdf]. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*.
8. Brown, C., George-Curran, R. & Smith, M.L. (2003). The role of emotional intelligence in the career commitment and decision- making process. *Journal of Career Assessment*, vol.11, no.4. <http://jca.sagepub.com/content/11/4/379.abstract>
9. Chatman, J. (1991). *Matching People and Organization: Selection and Socializing in Public Accounting Firm*. North-western University. <http://www.jstor.org/pss/2393204>

10. Edwin, H. (2001). Human Resources and Labor Relations. National Career Development Association.http://www.freepatentsonline.com/article/Career_Development_Quarterly/72703618.html
11. Encyclopedia. (2011). Theory of Multiple Intelligence. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Theory_of_multiple_intelligences
12. Goleman, D. (1998). Working with emotional intelligence [E-Book].
13. Gosling, M. (2006). Measuring emotional intelligence of managers in Singapore and the application of emotional intelligence for individual and organization effectiveness [pdf]. School of Management, PhD thesis, University of South Australia.
14. Granovetter, M., (1973). Strength of Weak Ties. American Journal of Sociology. [Abstract only]. Available through Journal Storage.
15. Hall, D. T. (1996). Protean careers of the 21st century. Academy of Management Executive. <http://www.jstor.org/pss/4165349>
16. Hall, D. T., & Chandler, D. E. (2005). Psychological success: When career is calling. Journal of Organizational Behavior.
17. Hall, D. T., & Moss, J. E. (1998). The new protean career contract: Helping organizations and employees adapt. Organizational Dynamics.
18. Hall, D., T. (2004). Protean Career. Available through: Sloan Work and Family, Research Network.http://wfnetwork.bc.edu/encyclopedia_entry.php?id=249
19. Hansen, M., (1999). The Search-Transfer Problem: Role of Weak Ties in Sharing Knowledge across Organization Subunits. Administrative Science.
20. Heslin, P. A. (2005). Conceptualizing and evaluating career success. Journal of Organizational Behavior.
21. Holland, J. L. (1997). Making vocational choices: A theory of vocational personalities and work environments [pdf]. Odessa, FL: Psychological Assessment Resources.
22. Hughes, E. C. (1937). Institutional office and the person. American Journal of Sociology. <http://www.jstor.org/pss/2768627>
23. Hughes, E. C. (1958). Men and their work. Glencoe, IL: Free Press.
24. Jordan, P.J., Ashton-James, C.E., Ashkanasy, N.M. (n.d.). 'Evaluating the Claims: Emotional Intelligence in the Workplace'. K.R.Murphy ed.2006. A Critique of Emotional Intelligence, what are the Problems and How they be fixed? [e-book]. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates. New Jersey.
25. Lawrence, B. S. (1984). Age grading: the implicit organizational timetable [pdf]. Journal of Organizational Behavior.
26. Lawrence, B. S. (1996). Organizational age norms: why is it so hard to know one when you see one.
27. Mayer, J. D., Roberts, R. D. & Barsade, S. G. (2008). Human abilities: emotional intelligence – Emerging research in emotional intelligence [pdf]. Annual Review of Psychology, Vol. 59. http://www.unh.edu/emotional_intelligence/EI%20Assets/Reprints...EI%20Proper/EI2008%20MayerRichardsBarsade%202008%20Draft%20Preprint.pdf
28. Mayer, J.D. & Salovey, P. (1997). What is emotional intelligence? Emotional development and EI: Educational implications. New York.
29. Mayer, J.D., Caruso, D.R. & Salovey, P. (1999). Emotional Intelligence Meets Traditional Standards for an Intelligence [pdf]. Intelligence, vol.27, no.4.
30. Mayer, J.D., Salovey, P. & Caruso, D.R. (2000). Models of emotional intelligence. Handbook of intelligence. Cambridge University Press.
31. Mayer, J.D., Salovey, P. (1990). Emotional Intelligence [pdf].
32. Mayer, J.D., Salovey, P., Caruso, D.R. & Sitarenios, G. (2001). Emotional intelligence as a standard intelligence emotion.
33. Nevitt, S. (1967). Education for Individual Development. New Dimension in Higher Education [pdf]. Duke University, Durham. North Carolina.
34. Parsons, F. (1909). Choosing a vocation. Boston, MA: Houghton Mifflin.
35. Patton, W., & Lokan, J., (2001). Perspectives on Donald Super's Construct of Career Maturity [pdf]. International Journal for Educational and Vocational Guidance.
36. Patton, W., & McMohan, M., (2006). Career Development and Systems Theory [pdf]. 2nd

- ed. Sense Publishers, Rotterdam.
37. Ruth, K., Wanberg, Connie R., Kantrowitz, & Tracy M. (2001). Job search and employment: A personality–motivational analysis and meta-analytic review. *Journal of Applied Psychology*. [Abstract only]. American Psychological Association.
 38. Savickas, M. (1997). *The Career Development* [pdf]. Ohio National Career Development Association.
 39. Seibert, S. E., Kraimer, M. L., & Liden, R. C. (2001). A social capital theory of career success. *Academy of Management Journal*.
 40. Senghas, S. (2007), Using the Ginzberg Theory of Occupational Choice to Determine your Career Path.
 41. Sorrensen, K.L., (2005). Predictor of Objective and Subjective Career Success: A Meta Analysis. University of Georgia, Athens.
 42. Stebbins, R. A. (1970). Career: the subjective approach. *Sociological Quarterly*.
 43. Stys, Y., & Brown, S.L. (2004). A Review of the Emotional Intelligence Literature & Implications for Corrections, Research Branch, Correctional Service of Canada. <http://www.csc-scc.gc.ca/text/rsrch/reports/r150/r150-eng.shtml>
 44. Sullivan, S. E. (1999). The changing nature of careers: a review and research agenda [pdf]. *Journal of Management*.
 45. Thorndike, E. L. (1934). *Prediction of vocational success*. Oxford University Press, New York.
 46. Urs, G. & Laurie, L., (1989). Predictors for Career Achievement in the Corporate Hierarchy [pdf]. Canada Employment and Immigration Commission, Ontario.
 47. Zeidner, M., Matthews G., & Roberts, R. (2004). Emotional intelligence in the workplace: A critical review. *Applied Psychology: An International Review*.